

of coconut frond or by foot. The field is then ready for dibbling.

Cow dung is cleaned of undigested grass or straw and trampled by foot into a paste. Water is added if required. The paste is leveled to a circle about 10 cm thick. Sprouted paddy seeds are then sprinkled over the paste. The seeds are mixed with the cow dung paste by foot. Then the cow dung paste is heaped with a spade and again leveled to a circle. The process is repeated three or four times. To determine if the seeds have been mixed uniformly, the farmer takes a pinch of the paste and examines it in a

bowl of water. The mixture is considered uniform when it shows 3–5 seeds/pinch.

The paste is then dibbled in the prepared beds by throwing it pinch by pinch, maintaining a uniform distance (40 to 45 hills/sq m) between hills.

If adequate cow dung is not available, fine tank silt is used for part of the paste. In 3 or 4 days, vigorous green sprouts emerge from the paste, giving the fields a green, carpety appearance. After 8 to 10 days, water is let in and allowed to stand in the furrows on either side of the beds. After about 2 weeks, water in the beds is increased to about 2 cm if

there are signs of weed growth or of white ant or cricket attack.

This sowing method is usually used for short-duration varieties that were not customarily transplanted in the past. It results in vigorous seedling emergence, better nutrient absorption in early stages, and survival during periods of water scarcity. Irrigation and drainage are more efficient because the furrows on both sides of the beds allow uniform moisture control. The method also allows freedom of movement for field operations. **W**

The relationship of *khaira* incidence in rice to phosphorus levels and farmyard manure applications

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Khaira, an ailment attributed to zinc deficiency in plants, is common in the Mollisols of the *tarai* region of northern India. Phosphorus becomes more soluble on submergence. At high levels, it has reportedly reduced drastically the uptake and translocation of zinc to the shoots of rice plants.

In a field trial, the response of rice (variety IR24) to nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium fertilizers under artificially created soil fertility levels was studied. The levels were different amounts of the three nutrients and farmyard manure that had been applied to four plots (each consisting of 0.2 ha of an 0.8-ha experimental plot) during previous crop seasons. One plot received farmyard manure and fertilizer phosphorus, the second received high levels of phosphorus only, the third was rich in inorganic residual nitrogen, and the fourth received no fertilizer or manure during the previous years. Thus the experimental plots varied widely in available soil phosphorus. Each of the four plots was subdivided into 43 plots of equal size and response of rice to soil and fertilizer nutrients was studied.

Effect of levels of soil and fertilizer phosphate and farmyard manure on the incidence of *khaira*

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Phosphorus levels ^a (kg P/ha)	Plots affected by <i>khaira</i> (no.)			
	No plants affected	Fewer than 25% plants affected	Fewer than 50% plants affected	Almost all plants affected
0– 25	44	3	0	0
26– 50	20	15	8	1
51– 75	7	4	5	3
76– 100	2	1	8	3
101– 125	0	0	0	5
Farmyard manure applied in previous years	43	0	0	0

^a (Olsen's soil P + fertilizer P).

Interesting trends were noted in the incidence of *khaira* and levels of soil and fertilizer phosphorus (Olsen's P and single superphosphate, respectively) on the one hand, and in the previous year's application of farmyard manure on the other (see table).

The plot where farmyard manure had been applied in previous years had no incidence of *khaira* even at high levels of soil and fertilizer phosphorus. But in the plots with no farmyard manure, the relationship between *khaira* incidence and phosphorus levels was positive. At phosphate levels below 25 kg P/ha, there was almost no incidence of *khaira*. The few plots where it occurred were only mildly affected. As the phosphate level increased, the number of cases and the severity increased. At the highest phosphate level (100 to 125 kg P/ha), all

plots were severely affected.

Farmyard manure seems to have increased the availability or translocation, or both, of zinc to rice plants. Even at phosphate levels as high as 100 to 125 kg P/ha, no incidence of *khaira* was observed. Possible reasons are being investigated. **W**

Invitation to authors

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